

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES FOR TEACHING IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will talk about how to use modern technologies of shooting for young students in English lessons in school and higher education and how to apply them in practice in the educational system.

At the present stage of the development of society, the educational system should correspond to the modern needs of the state, society and family. Education of the 21st century implies the development of universal educational actions, the acquisition of basic competencies that are the basis for self-development and continuing education, the development of communicative qualities and information skills of the individual. Among the many academic disciplines, the subject "foreign language" occupies a special place.

In the process of studying foreigners, students do not acquire knowledge about the basics of science, but form the ability and skills to use someone else's language as a means of communication, a means of obtaining new and useful information. The task of the teacher is to arouse interest in educational activities, to achieve the manifestation of activity in the study of material by students. Therefore, the teacher often faces questions about how to ensure the effectiveness and interest of the lesson. Currently, it is very difficult to maintain students' interest in studying. The complexity of the labor of teachers is the development of a passion for knowledge in each child, stimulation not only to receive ready-made information and knowledge, but also to develop independently, self-study, search for solutions, analyze and draw conclusions. And in our time, these goals cannot be achieved without the use of modern educational technologies.

This is due to the large and rapid leap in the development of information and communication technologies and the modernization of the educational system. In our digital age, you cannot do without digital education. The introduction and application of new information and communication methods and teaching methods will undoubtedly help to increase motivation and independent activity in teaching. Currently, the Internet provides excellent opportunities for teaching a foreign language, since with its help the opportunity to communicate live in the language under study is provided, the opportunity to use all kinds of real materials and many educational resources. So, based on the principle of independence of knowledge, I built a lesson on the topic

"grammar: Times of the Present Perfect group". The methodological goal of the lesson was to show the application of collaborative teaching technology at the stage of communicative development competencies, teaching grammatical skills using electronic simulators. The main task of the lesson was to stimulate the cognitive activity of students, taking into account their capabilities, personal interest and the practical significance of the results of work.

The goals and objectives of the lesson were achieved by applying the basic principles of a systematic-activity approach to teaching in the lesson, the introduction of interactive methods and methods into the structure and content of the lesson stimulated the cognitive motivation of students and helped to achieve the planned results. At the initial stage of the lesson, methods of communicative technologies such as "communicative attack" and "problem questioning" were used to create a comfortable state of communication and create a mood for active work in the lesson. The application of the technology for the development of critical thinking ("mental attack", the formation of a problem question) helped to obtain the individual experience of students through a non-standard approach to activating the educational process and performing tasks at the stage of determining the topic, purpose and effective methods of work in the lesson in order to achieve good results. For this, at the beginning of the lesson, students were given homework for the next lesson and asked questions: they could do it immediately without prior preparation, and what material they had to learn to complete this task.

After identifying the topic of the lesson together, students determine the purpose of the lesson and what tasks they set for the lesson. Everything is written in a notebook and spoken. In addition, in order to repeat and strengthen the grammatical material, that is, in the lesson, it was necessary to study the construction formula and the circumstances of the use of Present Perfect Continuous, and the difference have been, there was another motivation for active work in the use of gone to and have been in - there was the formation of a problematic issue and Students have determined for themselves an effective way to work in the lesson on the basis of assignments and are divided into three groups. Each team issued a card with a task to repeat and practice. To update knowledge and explain the new material, the technology of collaborative training was used — independent study and training of the grammatical rule, discussion in the team and explanation of this rule for other members of the small group.

Students, after dividing into groups and receiving assignments, begin to perform with the help of educational presentation with hyperlinks to laptops and theoretical and practical materials. Each group learns, discusses and performs training exercises together. The use of the method of collaborative teaching in the lesson ("we are in a group") made it possible to stimulate the cognitive activity of students, taking into account their capabilities, personal interest, the practical importance of work results, and also helped to unite the team and develop the ability to work in a team, where everyone's achievements are important for The next stage of the lesson is the primary combination of knowledge with external pronunciation — work with supporting slides. After completion, students in each group verbally submit the material they learned for other groups based on the slide, with "listeners" writing the information briefly in a notebook and answering their questions or the teacher's questions. Physical moments should be spent in the lesson - the use of the element of health technology will help create a comfortable atmosphere in the lesson and increase the activity of

performing further tasks. Rest is practiced after skills of practicing grammatical knowledge-practical work, the use of collaborative teaching technology (mutual assistance and verification in the construction of their tasks). Students practice the knowledge gained independently, performing tasks using a free online curriculum service that allows them to interactively develop grammatical skills. Tasks are carried out during joint discussion and mutual verification in the group. The use of information and communication technologies (working with laptops, presentations and electronic simulators) at the stage of acquaintance, training and strengthening, grammatical material made it possible to develop the skills of each member of the group to work independently in constant contact with the same group and other members of the class as a whole.

This also made it possible to focus on the active mental activity of students from different types of reproductive exercises in the process of preparing their tasks in an electronic interactive simulator. At the stage of strengthening skills, students create their tasks with the help of the Learning Apps service, the service provides material according to the proposed template, which allows you to conveniently and easily create electronic interactive exercises for teaching grammar, and invites any participant in the other group to perform their tasks. At the end of the lesson, independent work is carried out to verify the knowledge gained and the results of the work - to individually complete the test task in the "My test" program and receive an assessment for the lesson. The use of the electronic Simulator "my test" for the final Test and assessment for the lesson made it possible to exclude the subjectivity of the teacher's assessment and objectively showed the result of mastering the lesson material. Summing up the results of the lesson, we reflect-students compare the delivered goals and objectives with the result of the lesson and assess whether the knowledge gained is sufficient for homework. The use of ICT technologies will undoubtedly help to learn foreign languages more efficiently and consciously. In such classes, the activity of the teacher changes, he is not a " translator " of knowledge, but organizes activities together with students. The teacher should draw up the lesson in such a way that the knowledge of children is the result of his own research, organize these searches, manage students, develop their cognitive activity, assess them and show self-esteem criteria, monitor the real growth of everyone's knowledge, create a collaborative environment kerak.va a good psychological climate.

References:

1. Cluster D-What is critical thinking
2. Strokan V. I-relevance of the use of Internet resources in teaching a foreign language